

1 **Helicase control by RNASE H1.**

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6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in cells over-expressing Rnaseh1 and in cells
7 depleted of Rnaseh1 to discover Rnaseh1 cellular functions. We demonstrate here disparate helicase
8 control by Rnaseh1. Rnaseh1 controlled both *Ddx10* and *Ddx11*, which appeared to exert antagonistic
9 helicase activity to that of *Ddx21*, a third Rnaseh1-regulated Ddx helicase.

10 Citations

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12 DDX21 coordinates transcription and ribosomal RNA processing. *Nature*, 518(7538), pp.249-253.

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